

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: The role and the effective usage of innovative technologies in teaching English are considered in this article. The Internet links, which are effectively used during the lessons, are also shown here.

Key words: innovative technologies, multimedia, Internet links, electronic resources, learning environment, motivation.

The digital age has changed the conditions of life, formation and education. Everything changes around, and accordingly, the attitude towards learning must change. The content of education in a modern comprehensive school remains unilateral; state standards based on an objective approach are morally outdated. Many modern teachers point to the lack of a competent approach, focused on the individuality of the student. Education at school does not give students a clearly expressed positive motivation to choose a life path, interests and prospects. Now, in the 21st century, the role of international education is growing. To raise own culture, to develop and to go forward is a vital necessity of our century and the young state. The same vital necessity is the study of foreign languages in order to keep pace with the times. Today, knowledge of English opens a window into a large global world with its wide flow of information and innovations. At the present stage of the development of the society, the modernization of the content of education in Uzbekistan is not connected with the innovation processes in the organization of teaching foreign languages. Therefore, the main goal of the modern teacher is to increasingly. Since the main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of a communicative culture of schoolchildren, the training of practical mastering a foreign language, the use of computer technology, Internet resources is the best approach in teaching. It's been quite a few years since a computer entered our life, and we no longer imagine a modern lesson without the use of information technology. ICT becomes an integral tool in increasing students' interest and developing visual-figurative thinking. Everyone understood that the use of ICT in the learning process has the potential to activate cognitive, intellectual and independent activities of students. Information technology makes it is possible to change significantly the forms and methods of academic work. In the education system ICT can be divided into two types: hardware (computer, printer, scanner, camera, video camera, audio and video tape recorder, etc.) and software (electronic textbooks, simulators, test environments, information sites, search systems Internet, etc.). Nowadays the computer is an effective assistant and

integral part of everyone, which allows to improve the quality of training and the effectiveness of control. Currently, the use of computers in the educational process is very important. I want to focus on the use of computer presentations in the educational process. The use of presentations allows to every teacher to intensify mastering of educational material by students and conduct classes at a qualitatively new level, instead of using a regular blackboard projecting slide films from the computer screen to a large wall-mounted screen or a personal computer (laptop) for each student. Colorfully designed presentations (using animation effects, in the form of text, a diagram, a graphic, a drawing.) solve the problem of using visual material. For example, if you previously cut and paste pictures on the board, then now you can find pictures with the help of Internet and insert them on the slide right away. If there is a lot of pictures, then make a few slides. At the lessons of the introduction of new material, one can use the following educational programs: great help in teaching phonetics, articulation, rhythmic intonation pronunciation skills, to increase the motivation of students to learn English is provided by the program «Professor Higgins. English without an accent» The interactive course» choose the methods and forms of organizing the learning activity of trainees, which optimally meet the goal. In recent years, the usage of new information technologies in schools has been raised Round-up (publisher Pearson Education Limited, Longman), consisting of several disks of different levels, is a great help in studying and fixing grammar. Exercises are arranged according to grammatical themes. Advantages of the course are the ability to check their answers and summarizing the results of the tasks with computers. Interactive course «Way Ahead» (Macmillan publishing house) — there are six levels of this course including games, crosswords, fascinating exercises for fixing grammatical and lexical material in a game form. Interesting and exciting is a sound and graphic design of the program. In the language laboratory there are disks with various type of educational programs. This is an important and extensive addition to the training process. The educational programs provide a large number of exercises for grammar and vocabulary. These programs are very easy to use, you need minimal computer skills, which is very important when working with a group of students. There are materials for all classes that are divided into modules, but their content is very simple and not very clear. Now let's move on to the issue of using the Internet for teaching English. Today, new methods of using Internet resources are opposed to traditional teaching foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real life situations that will stimulate the study of the material and develop adequate behavior. Now everyone understand that the

Internet has tremendous information capabilities and no less impressive services. Whichever way we relate to the Internet, we have to recognize the fact that the worldwide network has become an integral part of modern reality. Many students have long appreciated all the advantages of the Internet and use its services actively in their educational process, while for teachers the space of this world web remains mostly unknown, unfamiliar and to some extent frightening. What kind of help the Internet can provide depends on how we use it for solving didactic tasks. These days every modern teacher uses widely the resources of the global Internet. Preparing messages, students filter a lot of information, if they need to listen to music, and most often view photos. Such tasks for students can use the preparatory stage for the lesson, for example, in combination with the project method, allowing students to apply practically for their knowledge and skills. This is one of the forms of research organization and cognitive activity, in which group activity is successfully realized that allows to increase the motivation for learning a foreign language. In the center of such a work process stands the student himself, with the opportunity to freely express his opinion and practical usage of foreign speech. Thus, without the use of ICT in the teaching process, it is difficult to imagine modern English lessons. Their use expands the scope of the educational process, increases its practical focus. The use of ICT and Internet resources in the English lesson allows me to more fully implement a whole range of methodological, pedagogical and psychological principles. The usage of computers in English educational programs increases the effectiveness of solving communicative problems, develops different types of speech activity of students, and forms a stable motivation for students to learn foreign language activities in class. In the 21st century, the society makes ever higher demands on the practical knowledge of English in everyday communication and in the professional sphere. The volumes of information are growing, and often routine ways of its transfer, storage and processing are ineffective. The use of information technology reveals the enormous capabilities of the computer as a means of learning. But we must not forget that the use of multimedia technologies can not provide a significant pedagogical effect without a teacher, since these technologies are only ways of teaching. The computer in the educational process is not a mechanical teacher, a tool that enhances and expands the possibilities of its teaching activity.

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